

Supplementary File – Manuscript Production of Dental Prosthesis in Primary Health Care in Brazil

Table 1: Comparison of the Mean Annual Rates of Dental Prostheses Installation Among Adults and Elderly People According to Sociodemographic Characteristics and Oral Health Service Characteristics, Excluding Municipalities with Extreme Indicator Values

	Mean annual installation rate of dental prostheses among adults (n=1447)	Mean annual installation rate of dental prostheses among elderly (n=1112)
Sociodemographic characteristics		
Population size		
Up to 20,000 inhabitants	5,55 (6,24)	16,32 (14,93)
> 20,000 to 50,000 inhabitants	2,16 (3,89)	7,45 (11,03)
> 50,000 to 100,000 inhabitants	0,98 (2,02)	4,44 (8,14)
> 100,000 inhabitants	0,39 (1,18)	2,05 (6,01)
p-value (Kruskal-Wallis)	0.0001	0.0001
Social Vulnerability Index		
Very low vulnerability	5,52 (6,25)	13,76 (14,37)
Low vulnerability	5,12 (5,93)	14,42 (14,74)
Medium vulnerability	3,47 (5,22)	12,01 (14,59)
High vulnerability	3,40 (5,58)	10,14 (12,60)
Very high vulnerability	2,15 (4,20)	9,18 (13,52)
p-value (Kruskal-Wallis test result)	0,0001	0,0006
Oral health service characteristics		
Presence of CEO		
No	4,65 (5,89)	14,31 (14,57)
Yes	0,88 (2,34)	3,51 (7,98)
p-value (Mann-Whitney)	<0.001	<0.001
Presence of LRPD		
No	3,24 (5,22)	10,03 (12,67)
Yes	4,17 (5,70)	13,26 (14,79)
p-value (Mann-Whitney)	0,0066	0,0093

Table 2: Spearman Correlation Coefficients (Between Two Quantitative Variables) and Polychoric Correlation (Between Ordinal Variables) Between Sociodemographic and Oral Health Service Variables and the Annual Rates of Dental Prosthesis Installation in Adults and Elderly, Excluding Municipalities with Extreme Indicator Values

Spearman correlation	Annual dental prosthesis installation rate among adults	Annual dental prosthesis installation rate among elderly
Total population	- 0.6245*	- 0.5497*
Number of CEO	- 0.4709*	- 0.4523
Number of LRPD	+ 0.0659*	+ 0.0686*
Coverage of oral health services in PHC	+ 0.3469*	+ 0.3040*
Polychoric correlation		
IVS (higher index, higher social vulnerability)	- 0.2786*	- 0.1587*
Population size (higher value, larger population size)	- 0,5761*	- 0,6048*

*Asterisks indicate statistically significant correlation coefficients